

1 **Supplementary information**

2 **Manuscript title: Zona glomerulosa derived Klotho modulates aldosterone synthase** 3 **expression in young female mice**

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19 **Supplementary table 1.** Mouse primer and probe sequences used for qPCR.

Gene	Primer (5'-3')	Probe (5'-3')
<i>Cyp11b1</i>	Mm01204952_m1 (Applied Biosystems™, Thermo Fisher Scientific)	
<i>Cyp11b2</i>	Mm01204955_g1 (Applied Biosystems™, Thermo Fisher Scientific)	
<i>Nr4a1</i> (<i>Ngf1b</i>)	Mm01300401_m1 (Applied Biosystems™, Thermo Fisher Scientific)	
<i>Nr4a2</i> (<i>Nurr-1</i>)	Mm00443060_m1 (Applied Biosystems™, Thermo Fisher Scientific)	
<i>Renin</i> (<i>Ren-1</i>)	Forward: ACC TTC AGT CTC CCA ACA CG Reverse: CAA GGA AGG CCT CTT TGT GA	CCT TTG AAC GAA TCC CGC TCA AGA A
<i>Klotho</i>	Mm01218497_m1 (Applied Biosystems™, Thermo Fisher Scientific)	
<i>StAR</i>	Mm00441558_m1 (Applied Biosystems™, Thermo Fisher Scientific)	
<i>Ppib</i>	Mm00478295_m1 (Applied Biosystems™, Thermo Fisher Scientific)	

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22 **Supplementary table 2.** Human primer and probe sequences used for qPCR.

Gene	Primer (5'-3')	Probe (5'-3')
<i>HPRT1</i>	Hs02800695_m1 (Applied Biosystems™, Thermo Fisher Scientific)	
<i>CYP11B1</i>	Hs01596406_gH (Applied Biosystems™, Thermo Fisher Scientific)	
<i>CYP11B2</i>	Hs01597732_m1 (Applied Biosystems™, Thermo Fisher Scientific)	
<i>Klotho</i>	Forward: GGG ACC ACC AAG AGA GAT GAT GCC Reverse: CGA AAC CAT CCA TGA GGG ACC AT	ACC TTA AAA GCC ATC AAG CTG GAT GGG

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